

**ABOUT THE METHOD OF TEACHING TO STUDENTS THE SUBJECT
OF CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS**

Rakhimova Feruza Saidovna

**senior teacher of Tashkent university of information technologies after
named Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi**

Islamova Odila Abduraimovna

**associate professor of Tashkent university of information technologies
after named Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi**

Abduganieva Ozoda Ibragimovna

**senior teacher of Tashkent university of information technologies after
named Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi**

Iskandarov Sirojiddin Sharafaddin oqli

a student of the Faculty of Software

Engineering of Tashkent Perfect University

The topic of correlation and regression analysis is one of the important topics of probability theory and mathematical statistics. When going through this topic, the types of connections between quantities and their differences are explained first. Important concepts of functional connection, statistical connection, statistical connection are given.

If each value of one quantity corresponds to only one value of the second quantity through any number, such a connection is called a functional connection.

An example. Circumferential length C and its radius R are two quantities, then the functional connection between these quantities is written as follows. For example: $C = 2\pi R$, where each value of the radius R of the circle corresponds to a single value of the length C of the circle using the rule of multiplying it by.

Unfortunately, not all quantities found in nature are functionally related.

If a change in one quantity leads to a change in the distribution law of another quantity, such a relationship is called a statistical relationship.

For example. if we define X the amount of mineral fertilizer applied to one hectare of land as , and the amount of productivity Y obtained from this land as cannot be associated with a relationship. In such cases, statistical correlation is considered.

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After mastering the connections, students will be shown how to make a correlation table.

Consider a two-dimensional sample: $(x_1, y_1), (x_1, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_m)$, or in tabular form:

Y / X	x_1	x_2	...	x_n
y_1	n_{11}	n_{21}	...	n_{n1}
y_2	n_{12}	n_{22}	...	n_{n2}
...	...	...	...	...
y_m	n_{1m}	n_{2m}	...	n_{nm}

Here n_{ij} - in the given sample (x_i, y_j) number of elements.

Using the correlation table, the concept of conditional average value is introduced as follows: $\bar{Y}$ of the amount $X = x_1$ as the conditional mean value when the value is accepted $\bar{Y}(X = x_1) = n_{11} \cdot y_1 + n_{12} \cdot y_2 + \dots + n_{1m} \cdot y_m$, is said to. It is clear from this definition that if the sample is given, it will not be difficult to calculate its conditional mean values.

After that, the concepts of making the regression equation and the regression line are given.

X the conditional Y average value of the quantity also changes, i.e

$\bar{Y}(X = x) = f(x)$ - this is an equation Y of the amount X is called a regression equation against a quantity. The graph of this function is called a regression line.

When studying economic processes, it is necessary to look at two or more interrelated factors. Usually these factors are related to each other. If the regression lines of Y on X and Y on X are both straight lines, then the correlation is called a linear correlation. Now using the method of least squares a_0, a_1 - find the coefficients and solve the regression equation.

Let's take a closer look at the linear regression equation..

$\bar{Y}(X = x) = a_0 + a_1x$, here a_0, a_1 - linear function coefficients. The coefficients of this linear function are practically unknown, and they depend on the condition of being closest to the sample elements of the linear regression graph, i.e. a_0, a_1 -- parameters $Q^2 = \sum (Y_i - a_0 - a_1x_i)^2$ - we find from the condition of reaching the minimum of the quadratic form. This method is called the Legendre or least squares method.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial Q^2}{\partial a_0} = \sum_{i=1}^n 2(Y_i - a_0 - a_1x_i)(-1) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial Q^2}{\partial a_1} = \sum_{i=1}^n 2(Y_i - a_0 - a_1x_i)(-x_i) = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \bar{Y} - a_0 - a_1\bar{x} = 0 \\ \overline{XY} - a_0\bar{x} - a_1\bar{x}^2 = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} a_0 = \bar{Y} - a_1\bar{x} \\ \overline{XY} - (\bar{Y} - a_1\bar{x})\bar{x} - a_1\bar{x}^2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} a_0 = \bar{Y} - a_1\bar{x} \\ \overline{XY} - \bar{Y}\bar{x} + a_1\bar{x}^2 - a_1\bar{x}^2 = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} a_0 = \bar{Y} - a_1\bar{x} \\ \overline{XY} - \bar{Y}\bar{x} + a_1(\bar{x}^2 - \bar{x}^2) = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} a_0 = \bar{Y} - a_1\bar{x} \\ \overline{XY} - \bar{Y}\bar{x} = a_1(\bar{x}^2 - \bar{x}^2) \end{cases} \Rightarrow$$

$$\begin{cases} a_0 = \bar{Y} - a_1\bar{x} \\ a_1 = \frac{\overline{XY} - \bar{Y}\bar{x}}{\bar{x}^2 - \bar{x}^2} = \frac{\overline{XY} - \bar{Y}\bar{x}}{S_x^2} \end{cases} .$$

Found a_0, a_1 we put the values of in the linear regression equation.

$$\bar{Y}(X) = \bar{Y} - a_1 \bar{x} + a_1 x \Rightarrow \bar{Y}(X) - \bar{Y} = a_1(x - \bar{x}) \Rightarrow \bar{Y}(X) - \bar{Y} = \frac{\overline{XY} - \bar{Y} \bar{X}}{S_x^2} (x - \bar{x}).$$

We introduce the following definition: $r_b = \frac{\overline{XY} - \bar{X} \cdot \bar{Y}}{S_x \cdot S_y}$ - sample correlation

coefficient. $\bar{Y}(X) - \bar{Y} = r_b \cdot \frac{S_y}{S_x} (x - \bar{x})$ - is the equation of the straight line closest to

the given choice among all the straight lines.

We find the regression equation for the example below

Size $n=5$ of the selection $x_i: 1 \quad 1,5 \quad 3 \quad 4,5 \quad 5$
 $n_i: 1,25 \quad 1,4 \quad 1,5 \quad 1,75 \quad 2,25$

Find the regression equation of X on Y according to the distribution.

To solve, we first make the following table based on the data:

x_i	y_i	x_i^2	$x_i y_i$
1	1,25	1	1,25
1,5	1,4	2,25	2,1
3	1,5	9	4,5
4,5	1,75	20,25	4,875
5	2,25	25	11,25
$\sum_i = 15$	$\sum_i = 8,15$	$\sum_i = 57,5$	$\sum_i = 26,975$

Putting the calculated values in the table into the formula, we find the following:

$$\rho_{yx} = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} = \frac{5 \cdot 26,975 - 15 \cdot 8,15}{5 \cdot 57,5 - 15^2} = 0,202,$$

$$b = \frac{n \sum x_i^2 \sum y_i - \sum x_i \sum x_i y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} = \frac{5 \cdot 57,5 \cdot 8,15 - 15 \cdot 26,975}{5 \cdot 57,5 - 15^2} = 1,024.$$

Then the regression sampling equation: $\bar{y}_x = 0,202x + 1,024$.

After that, it is appropriate to give the students tables in separate options for their independent study, and to strengthen their knowledge on this topic. In this case, students can solve the problem using existing software and find a solution by creating the appropriate programs themselves. The advantage of this is that the regression line corresponding to the found equation is accurately created with the help of computer technology.

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